

Iraqi Peer Review Journal ISSN 1817 - 5562

The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine

The Official Journal of The Iraqi Ministry of Health

Volume 1 Number 3 December 2005

The Iraqi Journal of Medicine has agreed the use of the uniform requirements of manuscripts submitted to biomedical journals published by the INTERNATIONAL COMMITTEE OF MEDICAL JOURNAL EDITORS (ICMJE) and it's the first Iraqi peer journal listed by the ICMJE journal list. The first two issues of this journal appeared under the title of Al Karkh journal of Medicine

Executive Editor: Abdul Mutalib Mohammad Ali
Minister of Health

FOUNDING EDITOR: Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi
Member World Association OF Medical Editors

http://www.geocities.com/new_iraqijm

2005 © Postspecialty CME center in the University Hospital in Al-Kadhimiya. Ministry of Health

Our Experience with continuing medical education (CME) programme The CME center, University Hospital in AL-Kadhimiya

Dr.Aamir Jalal AL-Mosawi M.D., Ph.D.,

Physician in charge of Postspeciality CME center.

University Hospital in AL-Kadhimiya.

E.mail:kadhimiyaCME@hotmail.com

www.alkadhimiyaCME.4t.com

E-mail: kadhimiyaCME@hotmail.com

Medicine is witnessing a continuous and tremendous progress in all fields. The enormous strides in the understanding of the bases of diseases have permitted more rational bases for the diagnosis and management of various disorders. New diagnostic tools and new therapies are continuously emerging and contributing to improved patient care and management, and raising the hope for more specific and certain therapy for many disorders. The medical practice is rapidly changing and the aim of the CME center in our hospital is to encourage physicians in our hospital to keep pace with tremendous medical advances and changes in the scientific medical practices in all fields of medicine, So that they can play a critical role in the development of a unique and respectable Iraqi Medicine. Our CME center is encouraging all the scientific activities directed at achieving the above mentioned goal.

The CME programme is currently voluntary. However we have recently propose a scoring (marking) system for the assessment of the CME progress and CME scientific activities for specialist and consultant physicians that can be

used by the physicians themselves or by the directors or by the directors of the physicians in charge of the CME programme. Table (1) Postgraduate Lectures, Seminars, Workshops, conferences and courses aiming at the dissemination of knowledge about the recent advances in various field of medicine are strongly recommended and encouraged. Documentation of all clinical experiences including, the reports of the rare clinical disorders and reports of clinical trials and researches are important contributing factor to the development of medical practices and dissemination of useful medical knowledge.

The New Iraqi Journal of medicine the official journal of the official peer review journal of the Iraqi Ministry of health will help all qualified physicians here and elsewhere in documenting their clinical, research experiences and making it readable and citable outside.

The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine of Medicine is the first Iraqi peer review journal listed by the ICMJE, and currently it the only Iraqi peer review journal printed and distributed by the Ministry of Health.

Table (1): A new scoring system for CME programme achievement

CME activities	Type and setting	Marks(Scores)	Notes
1-Publications in peer review			
Research (clinical study).	In international peer review medical Journal.	70	For multi-author papers the marks are divided by the number of contributors.
	In local Iraqi or Arabian Medical Journal.	40	
Case reports and reviews.	In International medical Journal.	35	= =
	In Local Iraqi or Arabian Journal.		
2-Conferences workshops and symposia			
Made Presentation	International	40	
	Local Iraqi(Arabian)	25	
Attendance	International	20	
	Iraqi and Arabian	15	
3- Lectures(Lectured)	CEM Lectures	10	CEM Lectures should be based on more than 10 references (Journals not books).

Russell W. Chesney, M. D.

Prof. Russell W. Chesney

In this section, the editor, Dr. Al-Mosawi, invites a distinguished physician to contribute to the New Iraqi Journal of Medicine on a subject that is considered of interest to our readers. In this issue, Professor Chesney kindly wrote a paper about pediatric training and certification in the USA.

Dr. Chesney, a native of Knoxville, Tennessee, received his AB in Biology from Harvard College in 1963. He then attended the University of Rochester, where he took a year-out Fellowship in Renal Physiology and received his M.D. with Honors in 1968. He was a Pediatric Resident in the Harriet Lane Service at The Johns Hopkins Hospital from 1968-70 and 1972-73. From 1970-72, he was a Clinical Associate in Renal Biochemistry at the NIH (NICHD). He took a Fellowship in Pediatric Nephrology and Biochemical Genetics at the Montreal Children's Hospital of McGill University from 1973-75.

In 1975, he joined the faculty of the University of Wisconsin as a clinician-scientist in nephrology engaging in renal biochemical research and rose to Professor in 1981. In 1985, he became Professor and Vice Chair of Pediatrics at the University of California, Davis. He was appointed LeBonheur Professor and Chair of Pediatrics in 1988 at the University of Tennessee Health Sciences Center in Memphis, his current position.

Dr. Chesney became a member of the Society for Pediatric Research in 1976 and served as President from 1986-1987. A member of the American Pediatric Society, he has served on the Council since 1996 and was President from 2002-2003. He has participated in the Annual PAS meetings since 1972 and has presented many abstracts, sponsored others, served as a program moderator on numerous occasions and participated in plenary sessions and educational workshops. He has served as an officer of other organizations including the Midwest Society for Pediatric Research (Secretary-Treasurer, President), American Society of Pediatric Nephrology (Secretary-Treasurer, President) and Tennessee Chapter of the AAP (Council, President).

Dr. Chesney is a Diplomate and Member of the American Board of Pediatrics, serving on its Sub-Board in Nephrology and is currently Chair of the Board of Directors and Research Advisory Committee. He has also served as President and Vice President of the American Pediatric Society. He has been Secretary Treasurer and was President of the Association of Medical School Pediatric Department Chairs (AMSPDC) through January 2003. He has served on numerous national committees including the Pediatric Scientist Development Program Steering and Selection Committee, Scientific Advisory Committee of the National Kidney Foundation, National Kidney and Urology Diseases Advisory Board, General Medicine B Study Section (NIH), VA Merit Review

His ongoing research interests are in the areas of the 1) regulation of renal amino acid transport, 2) exploring gene-nutrient, transcriptional and translational mechanisms in regulating transporter synthesis, 3) inherited renal tubular disorders and 4) the physiology, biochemistry and of clinical application of vitamin D metabolites to childhood disorders of bone and mineral metabolism. He has published over 300 original peer-reviewed articles and 190 chapters. He is involved in the education of medical students, residents, post graduate fellows. He served as Vice Chair of the Future of Pediatric Education Task Force which

Committee in Nephrology (Chair) and several AAP Councils including Committee on Pediatric Research (Chair), Committee on Pediatric Education (Chair), Council in Federal Government Affairs and Board of the Children's Center for Health Research. He also serves as a member of the Public Policy Council of the

Federation of Pediatric Organizations. He also serves on the Child Health Finance Committee of the National Association of Children's Hospitals and Related Institutions and its Board of Directors. He has served on many editorial boards and served as Editor of Pediatric Nephrology and is currently Consulting Editor of Pediatrics.

recently published its findings concerning the lifelong education of pediatricians in the new century.

Dr. Chesney has received the E. Mead Johnson Award, the Nutrition Award of the AAP, the Founders Award of the Southern SPR, the Joseph St. Geme Leadership Award, the Henry Barnett Award and has been selected as a visiting professor at numerous medical schools.

He is married to Dr. P. Joan Chesney, a distinguished expert in pediatric infectious disease. They have three children.

The Training and Certification of Pediatricians in the United States of America

Russell W. Chesney, M.D. LeBonheur Professor and Chair of Pediatrics
The University of Tennessee Health Science Center 50 North Dunlap
Memphis, TN, USA 38103
Tel: 901-572-3106 Fax: 901-572-5028 E-mail: RChesney@utmem.edu

The Training Process for General and Subspecialty Pediatrics

The concept of residency training in the discipline of pediatrics has evolved over the past 95 years in the United States, resulting in a highly defined and organized training program of 36 months that prepares medical school graduates to become general pediatricians. Individuals who wish to be trained in a subspecialty, such as nephrology, will usually train for an additional 36 months in a fellowship. After training in general pediatrics and in subspecialty pediatrics in a prescribed and approved training program, those individuals may then sit for an exam, which certifies them as having achieved a certain standard. At present, there exist approximately 200 three-year pediatric residency programs of between 4 and 36 residents per year. Currently, 3000 trainees per year are in these programs. Of the 200 programs; approximately 125 are located within the medical United States and Puerto Rico. Approximately 75 programs are found in academic schools of the centers not physically located in but often affiliated with a medic. In addition, several residencies are located in military hospitals of the U.S. Army, U.S. Navy, and the U.S. Air Force. All residency sites have a program director and faculty consisting of general pediatricians and

subspecialty pediatricians. Among the subspecialties represented are neonatology, cardiology, neurology, allergy and immunology, critical care, developmental and neurodevelopmental pediatrics, endocrinology, nephrology, gastroenterology, genetics, infectious disease, pulmonology, hematology/oncology, and emergency medicine the requirements of a pediatric residency program are governed by the Residency Review Committee (RRC) of the Accreditation Council on Graduate Medical Education (ACGME). These requirements govern the fundamental makeup of each residency in each medical discipline (internal medicine, surgery, psychiatry, etc.) and are divided into institutional and specific specialty (e.g., pediatrics) guidelines. These requirements are reviewed every 5 years and are generally vetted by a number of pediatric organizations including the American Academy of Pediatrics, the American Board of Pediatrics, the American Pediatric Society, the Society for Pediatric Research the Ambulatory Pediatric Association and the Association of Pediatric Program directors. While the RRC promulgates the requirements, these other societies evaluate and make

both general and specific comments. By a process of compromise, new guidelines are established, published, and then approved by the ACGME.

An important role of the Pediatric RRC is to visit each program on site at least once every 5 years. If all program requirements are met, then the program is approved. Candidates for a pediatric residency will obviously wish to train in an approved residency program.

The 3-year residency has graded responsibilities each year. The first year a resident or intern functions in inpatient and outpatient rotations as the most junior trainee. He or she must be a graduate of a medical school and must have passed the USMLE (United States Medical Licensing Examination) parts I, II and III.

The internship year is possibly the most important in all of U.S. medical education, because the intern is the individual with the most direct responsibility for his/h and it is a continuous learning year. Rotations are generally for one month, and include rotations in the inpatient service, the preterm nursery, the normal neonatal nursery, the emergency department and outpatient rotations. During the second year, residents will spend months as a supervisory resident on an inpatient service, more time in the emergency department, electives in pediatric subspecialties, and possibly more time in the preterm nursery. During the 36-month residency, there are required rotations in behavioral and developmental pediatrics, adolescent medicine, and a pediatric intensive care unit. During the 36 months, no more than 6 months can be spent in the intensive care unit and the neonatal intensive care unit.

The third year of the residency is spent in a supervisory role on the inpatient units, in the nursery and in the

outpatient department, with the remaining months being spent on electives. After the 36 months of training, the program director approves each resident to sit for the American Board of Pediatrics examination.

Each year one to two individuals are chosen as the Chief Resident(s). These individuals play an important teaching and administrative role. In most programs, this individual is in his/her 4th year of training.

All residents receive a salary that is paid by the teaching hospital. The hospital then recovers this funding in the form of graduate medical education funding from the medical system, an insurance program that covers all individuals over 65 years of age or from U.S. government funding provided to children's hospitals.

WHY PHYSICIANS ARE CERTIFIED BY BOARDS

The concept of Board Certification of a physician in a discipline dates back more than 80 years. A certificate was awarded for life and indicated that the certificate holder had taken and passed a written examination and, often, an oral examination. This board certification indicates that a physician has met a national standard. The "Boards" of the major disciplines, such as Pediatrics, Medicine, Surgery, etc are bound together under the American Board of Medical Specialists (ABMS) which supervises 24 specialty boards.

The programs in which ABMS trainees are trained are carefully critiqued and evaluated by the ACGME – the Accreditation Council for Graduate Medical Education. The Residency Review Committees (RRC) are

appointed by the ACGME and review all residencies. An important concept to bear in mind is that individual physicians, are certified by “Boards” based upon their knowledge, skills, and attitudes, and that residency programs are accredited by the RRC and, hence, the ACGME and not by individual “Boards”. The individual physician is certified by the following process: training for a designated time period in an approved residency program, completing a prescribed curriculum, being approved to sit for a certifying examination by a program director, and passing a secure examination in a testing center. As time h the 1930’s, new concepts have been incorporated. Key among these are that the individual trainees have the attitudes and moral behavior required of an excellent physician (as attested by the program director) and that the certificate is time-limited; physicians must recertify to maintain their Board status. Similarly, training program required to renew their status with the RRC at five-year intervals, thus assuring that residency program development is ongoing. Most critical, however, is that the Board assures the public of the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of each physician who receives a certificate. Since the Board certifies physicians, it must have a slightly distant and objective relationship with medical-led professional societies. Hence, the American Board of Pediatrics is separate from the American Academy of Pediatrics, the American Board of Internal Medicine is separate from the American College of Physicians, and

so forth. Similarly, sub-boards are independent of subspecialty societies, e. g., ASN/ASPN, etc. All boards have non-physician members who represent the views of the public.

A specialty board can develop a subspecialty board. For instance, the American Board of Pediatrics (ABP) certifies pediatric nephrologists through the Sub-Board o Pediatric Nephrology. It is the role of the ACGME, through the RRC, to approve the length and content of each Nephrology fellowship program. This is how each program receives its accreditation. However, the examination that must be passed by each trainee is written by the members of the Sub-Board of Pediatric Nephrology and supervised by the American Board of Pediatrics. This process of training and certification is not influenced by professional societies or by pharmaceutical companies. The fee for the examination is paid by the trainee. This process assures the public of lack of undue influence by the profession on the certification process.

The Boards of clinical disciplines also have “third-tier” examination and certificates. “Third-tier” is defined as specialized skills within a sub-board of a discipline Under the American Board of Pediatrics are third-tier Boards in Toxicology and in Laboratory Medicine. A third-tier certificate also exists in Cardiac Electrophysiology within Internal Medicine/Cardiology. The American Society for Transplantation (AST) has been evaluating, approving, accrediting and credentialing fellowship programme in renal transplantation in Internal Medicine. If there is a need for third-tier certification in renal transplantation, the Board process

could serve as a mechanism by which the discipline of renal transplantation could be evaluated. While a third-tier certification process requires several timely steps and approval at several levels (Task Force of ABP,

APP Board of Directors, ABMS, ASPN members), serves as a mechanism of certification that ensures impartiality and is in keeping with established standards in the academic pediatric community.

In conclusion, the certification process involves a series of steps by which individual physicians can be evaluated by a specialty board, and the training program in which that physician trains is accredited by a residency review committee that is supervised by the ACGME. This process has been in place for many years (80+), has served pediatrics well, and is now being emulated by organized medicine in the nations of the European Union. Most importantly, the established processes ensure an important served pediatrics well, and is now being emulated by organized medicine in the nations of the European Union.

References

1. www.abp.org
2. www.aap.org
3. www.acgme.org
4. Chesney, RW: Working Group on the Follow Up to the FOPE II Recommendations: A Proposal to Develop This Process. Approved by the Federation of Pediatric Organizations, January 23, 2001

Factors associated with self mutilation

Ali Al-Ubadi Psychiatrist
Al- Yarmook teaching hospital
Baghdad, Iraq

Ghazi Aboud Psychiatrist
Al- Rashad Hospital
Baghdad, Iraq.
E-mail:ghazi957@yahoo.com

Abstract

Background: Self-mutilation is deliberate self-harm without the intent of death. The reported motivations for self-mutilation include punishment, tension reduction and mood improvement.

Aim of study: To study the psychological, educational, criminal & motivational factors associated with self inflicted wounds.

Patients and method: 24 male patients with self harm observed at Al-Rasheed hospital and Al-Yarmook teaching hospital during the period between June 2002 –March 2003 were enrolled in this study and interviewed by the authors. Evaluation included IQ assessment (Raven) and EEG recording.

Results: Tension reduction was the main motivational factor associated with self-cutting or burning. EEG study was normal in 21 patients, while I.Q ranged between (60 –110).14 patients (58%). All of them injured their upper limbs and 21 patients (88%) had been injured by sharp instrument.

The self-mutilator reports a range of motivations, including self-punishment, tension reduction, improvement in mood, and distraction from intolerable

were habituated on hallucinogens and 10 patients (42%) did the act due to internal tension.

Conclusion: Tension reduction was the main motivational factor associated with self-cutting or burning. All of mutilations were involved upper limbs and personality disorders were a common cause in the mutilators.

Key words: self mutilation motivational Factors

Introduction

Self-mutilation is deliberate self harm with out the intent of death [1].The most usual forms are cutting and burning. [2,3].Age at onset typically is between 14 – 24 years[4, 5].Self-mutilation is characterized typically by a sense of rising tension before the act and preoccupation with strong and persistent urges to hurt oneself [6]. At some point, the urge becomes overwhelming, the individual is no longer able or willing to resist, and he then engages in self-mutilation.

affects [2, 3]. Following the act, the individual usually reports feeling better and relieved [2, 3, 7, 8]. It has been speculated that self-mutilating behaviour

serves a coping function that is activated by an increase in emotional arousal [9,10]. Observations in non-human mammals have shown that self-mutilating behaviours may emerge as a consequence of deprived rearing conditions[11,12]. Thus, self-mutilating behaviour may be regarded as an unusual, but effective coping strategy for the self-regulation of hyper arousal and/or dissociative states and for regaining control over an otherwise uncontrollable stress response[13]. Linehan postulated that all deliberate self-harm ought to be considered on a continuum of lethality, regardless of the intention to die[14]. The most commonly used object is a knife, razor, glass piece, scissors, and ice pick are the other objects used[15]. Skin cutting appears to be the most common form of self-harm, occurring in at least 70% of individuals who harm themselves [4, 5,16,17, 18], and between 15% and 35% burn their skin [4, 5, 17, 18]. Self-inflicted wound commonly seen over the wrist, elbow, neck and the trunk [19]. Self-inflicted abdominal stab wounds usually cause non-lethal injuries but sometime result in significant injuries [15]. Psychotic and non-psychotic genital self-mutilation is well recognized in males but not in females [20]. The borderline personality has been described as not genuinely suicidal or life-threatening but primarily attention-seeking behaviour and manipulative[21]. The self-mutilating patients reported significantly greater frequency of physical punishment during

childhood but did not report more frequent sexual abuse [22].

Patients and Methods

24 patients (outpatients and inpatients) with self-mutilation were observed in Al-Rasheed Military hospital and Al-Yarmook teaching hospital during the period from June 2002 to March 2003. Their ages ranged from 18 to 33, 15 patients (62%) their ages ranged between 20 and 30 years, 6 patients (25%) their ages between 18-20 years and, 3 patients (13%) their ages ranged between 30-33 years. All of them were males. All the patients were interviewed by authors (psychiatrist) and clinically assessed; in addition to that EEG and I.Q (Raven) had been done.

Results

Past history: 2 patients (8 %) have sexual abuse at childhood 2 patients (8%) got closed head injury

Marital state (Figure-1): 17 patients (71%) were single, and 2 patients (8%) were married while 5 patients (21%) were divorced.

Scholastic Achievement (figure-2): 10 patients (42%) reached elementary school, 7 Patients (29%), who reached intermediate school, 2 (8%) Patients reached secondary school, 5 patients (21%) were illiterate.

Criminal history figure (3).

Intelligence Quotient (IQ): IQ ranged between 60 -110 .Only one patients is subnormal as in table (1).

I.Q level	No. of patients	Percentage %
-7060	1	4
70-90	14	58
90 -110	9	38

Types of mutilation (figure 4).

Substance abuse

Five patients (21%) have history of alcohol consumption, while 14 of them (58%) were habituated on hallucinogens especially artane (benzhixol), including one patient Committed homicide

Site of self-harm: An affected bodily part of mutilation is shown in table 2.

Parts of body	No. of patients	Percentage %
upper limb ,face, neck ,chest, abdomen	2	8
upper limb,neck,chest, abdomen	5	21
upper limb,chest,abdomen	9	38
Upper limb	7	29
Upper limb, neck, chest ,abdomen ,thigh, sexual organs	1	4

Motivation of act as shown in table 3.

motives	No. of patients	Percentage %
Aggression toward the self	7	29
Internal tension	10	42
Aggression toward others	4	17
Asking for help	1	4
None	2	8

Psychiatric diagnosis as shown in table 4.

Diagnosis	No. of patients	Percentage %
Acute psychosis	2	8
Psychosis &M.R	1	4
Borderline personality	2	8
Other personality disorder	15	63
Psychopathic personality	4	17

EEG was normal in 21 patients (88%) A generalized slow wave activity was present in one patient with mental retardation EEG was abnormal in 2 patients (8%) for whom C.T scan was done and it was normal.

Discussion

The finding that only male patients with self-mutilation was observed was unexpected, as it is often reported that self-harm is more common in women than men or difference in the prevalence for men and women [16, 18,23,24 25,26].In this community social causes could have forbidden females from coming to the hospital .

The patients aged from 18 – 33, but 62% of the patients aged 20 to 30 years. Judith Horrocks etal [27] reported slightly older than that reported elsewhere [28, 29].

Cutting the skin by sharp instrument were more common (88%) than other type and this was higher than the reported in other studies[4,5,16,17,18].While 8% of patients harm themselves by burning and this was less than the reported by other studies[4,5,17,18].As in previous studies the upper limb was the most common part of the body injured [29]. The multiple cutting was 66.5% in

Judith Horrocks study [27] while in our study was 71%.

Internal tension is the common motive (42%) for inducing self-mutilation [6]. and there is physiological evidence that self-harmers experience a reduction in tension after an episode of self-harm [2, 3, 7, 8, 16]

Self-mutilators have higher rates of personality disorder (88%),including borderline personality(8%),psychopathic personality (16%) and other personality disorder(62%).These findings are consistent with other studies([17,30].

Habituation on hallucinogens was present in (58%) and alcohol consumption in (21%) and these results were not differ from several studies which have reported association between substance abuse and deliberate self-harm [17, 31, 32]. These drugs decrease the pain and cause a state of dissociation explaining this association. Tantam and Whittaker reported that many patients have a history of sexual abuse [33], but in this study only 8% have such history. 58% had been in trouble with the police and this may be due to a lot of failure in school, military service and employment.

References

1. Paulino AF, Krolikowski FJ. Insertion of foreign body into the abdominal cavity. An unusual form of self-mutilation. *AmJ Forensic Med Pathol* 1995; 16:48-50.
2. Herpertz S: Self-injurious behavior: psychopathological and nosological characteristics in subtypes of self-injurers. *Acta Psychiatr Scand* 1995; 91:57-68.
3. Favazza AR: Repetitive self-mutilation. *Psychiatr Annals* 1992; 22(2):60-63.
4. Herpertz S: Self-injurious behaviour: psychopathological and nosological characteristics in subtypes of self-injurers. *Acta Psychiatr Scand* 1995; 91:57-68.
5. Favazza AR, Conterio K: Female habitual self-mutilators. *Acta Psychiatr Scand* 1989; 79:283-289.
6. Gardner DL, Cowdry RW: Suicidal and Para suicidal behaviour in borderline personality disorder. *Psychiatr Clin North Am* 1985; 8:389-403.
7. Favazza AR, Conterio K: Female habitual self-mutilators. *Acta Psychiatr Scand* 1989; 79:283-289.
8. Kemperman I, Russ MJ, Shearin E: Self-injurious behaviour and mood regulation in borderline patients *Personal Disord* 1997; 11:146-157.
9. Winchel RM, Stanley M: Self-injurious behaviour: a review of the behaviour and biology of self-mutilation. *Am J Psychiatry* 1991; 148:306-317.
10. van der Kolk BA, Perry JC, Herman JL: Childhood origins of self-destructive behaviour. *Am J Psychiatry* 1991; 148:1665-1671.
11. Jones IH: Self-injury: toward a biological basis. *Perspect Biol Med* 1982; 26:137-150.
12. Kraemer GW, Clarke AS: The behavioural neurobiology of self-injurious behaviour in rhesus monkeys. *Prog Neuropsychopharmacol Biol Psychiatry* 1990; 14(suppl):S141-S168.
13. Huether G: The central adaptation syndrome: psychosocial stress as a trigger for adaptive modifications of brain structure and brain function. *Prog Neurobiol* 1996; 48:569-612.
14. Linehan M: Suicidal people: one population or two? *Ann NY Acad Sci* 1986; 487:16-33.
15. Abdullah F, Nuernberg A, Rabinovici R. Self-inflicted abdominal wounds. *Injury* 2003; 34:35-9
16. Briere J, Gil E: Self-mutilation in clinical and general population samples: prevalence correlates, and functions. *Am J Orthopsychiatry* 1998; 68:609-620
17. Langbehn DR, Pfohl B: Clinical correlates of self-mutilation among psychiatric inpatients. *Ann Clin Psychiatry* 1993; 5:45-51.
18. Nijman HLI, Dautzenberg M, Merckelbach HLGJ, Jung P, Wessel I, Campo J: self-mutilating behaviour in psychiatric inpatients. *Eur Psychiatry* 1999; 14:4-10.
19. Karger B, Niemeyer J, Brinkmann B. Suicide by sharp force: typical and atypical features. *Int J Legal Med* 2000; 113:259-62.
20. Greilsheimer H, Groves JE: Male genital self-mutilation. *Archives of general Psychiatry* 36:441-446, 1979.

21. Bongar B, Peterson LG, Golann S, Hardiman JJ: Self-mutilation and the chronically suicidal patient; an examination of the frequent visitor to psychiatric emergency room. *Ann Clin Psychiatry* 1990; 2:217-222.
22. Barbara Stanley, Mare J. Gameroff, Venezia Michalsen, and J. John Mann: Are Suicide Attempters Who Self-mutilate a Unique Population? *American Psychiatric Association, Am J Psychiatry* 158:427-432, March 2001.
23. Ogunidipe LO: Suicide attempts vs. deliberate self-harm (letter). *Br J Psychiatry* 1999; 175:90.
24. Suyemoto KL: The functions of self-mutilation. *Clin Psychol Rev* 1998; 18:531-554.
25. Stanley B, Gameroff MJ, Michalsen V, Mann JJ: Are suicide attempters who self-mutilate a unique population? *Am J Psychiatry* 2001; 158:427-432.
26. Soloff PH, Lis JA, Kelly T, Cornelius J, Ulrich R: Self-mutilation and suicidal behaviour in borderline personality disorder. *J Personal Disord* 1994; 8:257-267.
27. Judith Horrocks, Sally Price, Allan House, David Owens: Self-injury attendances in the accident and emergency department. *Royal College of Psychiatrists, British Journal of Psychiatry* (2003) 183:34-39.
28. Robinson, A. & Duffy, J. (1989) A comparison of self-injury and self-poisoning from the Regional Poisoning Treatment Centre, Edinburgh. *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica*, 80, 272-279.
29. Taylor, D.M. & Cameron, P.A. (1998) deliberate self-inflicted trauma: population demographics, the nature of injury and a comparison with patients who overdose. *Australian and New Zealand Journal of Public Health*, 22, 120-125.
30. Herpertz S, Sass H, Favazza A: Impulsivity in self-mutilative behaviour: psychometric and biological findings. *Psychiatr Res* 1997; 31:451-465.
31. Zlotnick Cymatia JI, Zimmerman M: Clinical correlates of self-mutilation in a sample of general psychiatric patients. *Nerv Ment Dis* 1999; 187:296-301.
32. Turell SC, Armsworth MW: Differentiating incest survivors who self-mutilate. *Child Abuse Negl* 2000; 24:237-249.
33. D Tantam and J Whittaker: Personality disorder and self-wounding: *American Psychiatric Association, Am J Psychiatry* 1983; 140:867-872.

Idiopathic respiratory distress syndrome

Jassim Mohammad Jassim
Specialist Pediatrician
University Hospital in Al Kadhimiyia
Baghdad Iraq

Abstract

Background: Idiopathic respiratory distress syndrome (IRDS) occurs in 13% of all births

Aim of the study: To determine the incidence, sex distribution, associated risk factors and the outcome of IRDS in Al-Khansa'a Maternity and Children hospital in Al Mosul.

Patients and methods: 106 neonates, 61 Males (58%) and 45 females (42%) were admitted to the neonatal care unit in Al Khansa'a Maternity and Children hospital during the period from the first of March 2000 to the 31 December 2000. with the clinical diagnosis of IRDS were observed

Results: Higher incidence occurred in neonates of 31-32 week gestational age and mainly in male. Mothers aged from 20-24 years old have the highest incidence of affected neonates. 40 (37.7%) mothers aged between 20-40 year. The main factor associated with premature labour was Antepartum hemorrhage (APH) which was present in 20 mothers (22%). Previous history of IRDS in the family was present in 9 cases (8.5%). Cesarean section was a significant risk factor for IRDS. The majority of neonates (74%) with IRDS have APGAR score more above 7 after 1 minutes. 28 neonates (26%) have APGAR score below 7 at 1 and 7 minutes and 5 ($X^2 = 8.281$, $P = < 0.004$) (highly significant). 69(65%) neonates survived, and 37 (34.9%) died. The main cause of death was Apnea and respiratory failure = (59%).

Introduction

Idiopathic respiratory distress syndrome (IRDS) occurs in 1-3% of all births. This incidence is inversely related to the gestational age and birth weight. It occurs in 60-80% of infants less than 28 weeks of

gestational age. IRDS is responsible for the deaths of many Preterm infants throughout the world each year. Surfactant deficiency (decreased production and secretion) is the primary cause of IRDS. The disease has a wide spectrum of severity from mild respiratory distress lasting 2 or 3 days to a rapidly fatal illness causing death within few hours. The natural course of classic IRDS is that of increasing severity during the first 24-48hr of life followed by a period of stability lasting another 48hr before improvement occurs. Early provision of intensive observation and care of high risk newborn infants can significantly reduce morbidity and mortality due to IRDS. [1, 2,3,4,5, 6]. The Aim of this study is to determine the incidence, sex distribution, associated risk factors and the outcome of IRDS in Al - Khansa'a Maternity and Children hospital.

Patient and method: 106 neonates, 61 Males (58%), and 45 females (42%) were admitted to the neonatal care unit (NCU) in Al-Khansa'a Maternity and Children hospital during the period from the first of March 2000 to December 31 2000 with the clinical diagnosis of IRDS were observed. The clinical diagnosis of IRDS was made by the presence of 2 of the following signs: Tachypnea (R.R. > 60 / min.), Expiratory grunting, Sternal and intercostal recession, Cyanosis in room air, supported by the radiological findings which include fine granular, ground glass appearance, and air bronchogram. In addition to full history and clinical examination, chest X ray was done to all of them. Brain ultrasound was done to 4 in to confirm intraventricular haemorrhage. Blood culture and other investigations were done on need according to specific condition and complications occurred. Babies with transient

tachypnea of the newborn (TTN) and meconium aspiration were excluded from this study. All patients were treated with O₂, intravenous fluid antibiotics from this study. All patients were treated with O₂, intravenous fluid antibiotics (on empiric basis) as ampicillin with gentamicin or with third generation cephalosporin. Apnea were fully resuscitated by suction, incubation, and aminophylline when necessary. Blood transfusion was given to two patients with pulmonary hemorrhage (PH). The number of live deliveries during the period of the study in Al Khansa'a maternity and children Hospital was 14360 with 106 (0.75 %) of them suffering from IRDS.

Results

Higher incidence occurred in neonates of 31-32 wk gestational age and mainly in male. Table (1). Mothers aged from 20-24 years old have the highest incidence of affected neonates 40 (37.7%) mothers aged between 20-40 years 32 mothers (30 %) aged between 25-29 years, 17 mothers (16 %) aged between 35-39. years, 7 mothers (6.6 %) were under 19 years, 6 mothers (5.6 %) aged between 30-34 years, and 4 mothers (3.7 %) were above 40 years. The main factor associated with premature labour was Antepartum hemorrhage (APH) which was present in 20 mothers (22 %). Previous history of IRDS in the family was present in 9 cases (8.5%). Table (2) shows factors associated with premature labour. Cesarean section was a significant risk factor for IRDS. Table (3) shows the type of delivery of the baby with the number of affected patients. The majority of patients (74%) affected with IRDS have APGAR score more above 7. after 1 and 5 minutes. 28 neonates (26%) have APGAR score below 7 at 1 and 5 minutes ($X^2 = 8.281$, $P = < 0.004$ (highly significant). 69(65%) neonates survived, and 37 (34.9%) died. The main cause of death was Apnea and respiratory failure (RF) = (59 %). Table (4). Shows the causes of death. Most of neonates (35 %) required supplemental oxygen for 4 days. 49 neonates were 7 days or less. Those who stayed for longer time, most of them

were suffering from septicemia or because of delay oral feeding.

Table 1: Show Sex distribution of the patient according their birth weight and gestational age

Groups of Birth weights and gestational age	Total No.	Male	Fem ale	M :F
1 ≤0.999 kg (≤28 wk).	11	7	4	1.7 : 1
2 1 – 1.499 kg (29-30 wk)	27	14	13	1.07: 1
3 1500 –1.699 kg (31-32 wk)	30	19	11	1.7 :1
4 1.700 – 1.999 kg (33-34 wk)	26	14	12	1.1 :1
5 2 –2.499 kg (35-36 wk)	9	5	4	1.2 :1
6 ≥2.500 kg (≥37 wk)	3	2	1	2 : 1
Total	106	61	45	1.3 : 1
		(58%)	(42 %)	1

Table 2: Factors which associated with premature labour

Risk Factor.	Number of Patients.
APH	20 (16 accidental and 4 placenta previa)
Multiple Pregnancy	14 (12 twins,1 triplet,1 Quadriplet)
Infections	10 (4 systemic,4 vaginal,2 congenital)
Cervical incompetence.	5
Pre eclampsia.	5
Polyhydramnios.	6
Fetal distress.	8
Premature rupture of membrane	6
Mothers with more than 5 children.	7
Teenage Pregnancy.	5

Discussion

The incidence of IRDS in Al Khansa'a Hospital during the period of study was 0.75 % among all live birth deliveries, similar incidence was reported by Scope J W [7] The gestational age of about 89 % of the babies was less than 34 weeks and birth weight was less than 1.990 kg; 58 % were males and 42 % were females, their these findings are consistent with the finding by other studies [7, 8] Associated risk factors for premature deliveries and IRDS were present in 86

.mothers Young maternal age is considered a risk factor in this study. 47 mothers (44 %) were under 24 years. A similar finding was reported by Edwards A D [4].Antepartum Hemorrhage in this study was present in 20 mothers (22 %). This finding differs from previous papers [9] considering APH a rare risk factor for prematurity. Chronic hypertension or pregnancy induced hypertension was present in 5 mothers (6 %), which is similar to the previous report of Carvalho MA [10] The incidence of IRDS was higher among babies who did not require resuscitation. at birth (74%) but mortality rate was higher in those babies who had low APGAR SCORE at delivery and who required immediate resuscitation at birth (57%). The mortality rate was 35% while it was 10-30 % in other studies Carlow [11,12],this difference is attributed to the use of antenatal steroid , postnatal surfactant and the improved mode of ventilation as CPAP.

Conclusion: The incidence of IRDS was 0.75 % among deliveries. The highest incidence was in neonates who were 31-32 wks of gestation with a birth weight of 1.500- 1.699 kg and with male predominance. The main risk factors for IRDS were Antepartum hemorrhage, history of previous IRDS in the family and Cesarean section delivery The mortality rate was 35% and the main cause of death was apnea and respiratory failure

References

1- Stoll B J, Kliegman RM.The Fetus and the Neonatal Infant.In:Nelson Textbook of Pediatrics 19th edition2000 Behrman, Kliegman and Jenson: 451-552.
 2- McIntosh N. The Newborn. In: Forfar and Arneil's Textbook of Pediatrics 5 th 1998. 94 - 309. England.
 3- Edwards A.D Neonatal care for Obstetricians. In: Dewhursts Textbook of Obstetrics and

Gynecology for postgraduates .6th edition 1999 by Edmonds D. K. 361-72
 4- Pradeep M., Rajam, L, Sudevan P. Perinatal mortality a hospital based study. Indian Pediatr. 1995; 32 (10): 1091-4.
 5- Baker E, Wright V. Disorders of the respiratory tract Manual of Neonatal Intensive Care–Third edition–1993: 77– 166.
 6- Harris M. C. and Roth P. Neonatology Pediatric Secrets - Second edition - 1993- by Poline R. A. and Ditmar M. F. : 241-313.
 7- Scope J W .Respiratory Distress Syndrome. Brit.J.Hosp Med, 1970; 42: 579 – 84.
 8- Perelman R. H. Palta M.; Kirby R. and et al.– Discordance between Male and Female Deaths due to the Respiratory Distress syndrome. Pediatrics Vol. 78 No. 2 August 1986: 238-43
 9- Steer PJ.Preterm labour. Dewhursts Textbook of obstetrics and Gynecology for postgraduates. – Sixth edition – 1999 – by Edmonds: 291 – 7. England
 10- CarvalhoMA, Faundes A, Santos L C. Pregnancy induced hypertension and hyaline membrane disease. Int.J. Gynaecol obstet. 1997; 58 (2): 197-202.
 11- Dinwiddie – R. – Problems of the Newborn – Obstetrics by Ten Teachers - Fifteenth edition – 1992. By Lewis. T. and Chamberlain G. V. P.: 295 – 329. England
 12- Reynold, P. L. Allen – Controlled trial of CPAP given by facemask for infants with IRDS, Arch. Of disease in Children, 1977, 52: 373-8.

Table (3): Shows the type of delivery of the baby with the number of affected patient

Type of Delivery	No of deliveries	Total No of affected patients	No of deaths
N. V.	12265 (85 %)	81 (76 %)	28 (34 %)
C S	2095 (15 %)	25 (24 %)	9 (36 %)
Total	14360	106 (0.75 %)	37 (34.9 %)

$X^2 = 6.935$ $P = < 0.008$ (highly significant).

Table (3). Shows the causes of death.

Birth wt groups	No of Death	Causes of Death		
		Apnea &RF	Sepsis	IVH and /or PH
≤0.999 kg (≤28wk)	8 (72%)	4	2	2
1-1.499 kg (29-30wk)	11 (40%)	9	2	
1.5-1.699kg(31-32wk)	7 (23 %)	3	2	2
1.700-1.999 kg (33-34wk)	8 (30%)	4	1	3
2-2.499 kg (35-36wk)	2 (22%)	1	1	
2.500kg (≥37 wk)	1 (33%)	1		
Total	37(34.9%)	22 (59 %)	8(%)	7(19%)

Acknowledgment: The author acknowledges the great help of the editor Dr Aamir Jalal al Mosawi

in making this paper suitable for publication

Avian influenza A viruses in human: An emerging infectious disease

Aamir Jalal Al Mosawi MD, PhD

Director Postspecialty CME center

University Hospital in Al Kadhimiyia

Baghdad Iraq

E-mail:kadhimiyiaCME@hotmail.com.com

Pandemic of Influenza

An influenza pandemic is a global outbreak of disease that occurs when a new influenza A virus appears or “emerges” in the human population, causes serious illness, and then spreads easily from person to person worldwide. Pandemics are different from seasonal outbreaks or “epidemics” of influenza. Seasonal outbreaks are caused by subtypes of influenza viruses that are already in existence among people, whereas pandemic outbreaks are caused by new subtypes or by subtypes that have never circulated among people or that have not circulated among people for a long time. Past influenza pandemics have led to high levels of illness, death, social disruption, and economic loss. Influenza outbreaks are recorded virtually every year, although their extent and severity vary widely. Localized outbreaks take place at variable intervals, usually every 1 to 3 years. Except for the past two decades, global epidemics or pandemics have occurred approximately every 10 to 15 years since the 1918-1919 pandemic.

The most extensive and severe outbreaks are caused by influenza A viruses. In part, this predominance is a result of **the remarkable propensity of the H and N antigens of influenza A virus to undergo periodic antigenic variation.**

Major antigenic variations are referred to as antigenic shifts, which may be associated with pandemics and are restricted to influenza A viruses. Minor variations are called antigenic drifts. These antigenic changes may involve the hemagglutinin alone or both the hemagglutinin and the neuraminidase. In human infections, three major antigenic subtypes of hemagglutinins (H1, H2, and H3) and two of neuraminidases (N1 and N2) have been recognized. An example of an antigenic shift involving both the hemagglutinin and the neuraminidase is that of 1957, when the predominant influenza A virus subtype shifted from **H1N1** to **H2N2**; this shift resulted in a severe pandemic, with an estimated 70,000 excess deaths (i.e., deaths in excess of the number expected without an influenza epidemic) in the United States alone. In 1968, an antigenic shift involving only the hemagglutinin occurred (H2N2 to H3N2); the subsequent pandemic was less severe than that of 1957. In 1977, an H1N1 virus emerged and caused a pandemic that primarily affected younger individuals (i.e., those born after 1957).

H1N1 viruses circulated from 1918 to 1956. During most outbreaks of influenza A, a single subtype has circulated at a time. However, since

1977, H1N1 and H3N2 viruses have circulated simultaneously, resulting in outbreaks of varying severity. In some outbreaks, influenza B viruses have also circulated simultaneously with influenza A viruses.

The origin of pandemic strains is unknown. Given the marked differences between the primary structures of the hemagglutinins of different subtypes of influenza A viruses (H1, H2, and H3), it seems unlikely that antigenic shifts result from spontaneous mutations in the hemagglutinin gene. Because the segmented genome of influenza viruses may result in high rates of reassortment, it has been suggested that pandemic strains may emerge by reassortment of genes between human and animal viruses. There was concern that such reassortment might have occurred in 1997 in Hong Kong, where cases of infection caused by influenza virus A/H5N1 were detected in humans during an extensive outbreak of avian influenza A/H5N1 in poultry. However, only a few cases of A/H5N1 influenza in humans were documented, and the infection did not spread into the community. Influenza B viruses do not have an animal reservoir and do not undergo antigenic shifts [1, 2, 3, 4].

Transmission of Influenza A Viruses between Animals and People Influenza A viruses are found in many different animals, including ducks, chickens, pigs, whales, horses, and seals. However, certain subtypes of influenza A virus are specific to certain species, except for **birds which are hosts to all subtypes of influenza A**. Subtypes that have caused widespread illness in people either in the past or the current period are H3N2, H2N2, H1N1, and H1N2. H1N1 and H3N2 subtypes have caused

outbreaks in pigs and H7N7 and H3N8 viruses have caused outbreaks in horses. Therefore Influenza A viruses normally seen in one species sometimes can cross over and cause illness in another species. Until 1998, only H1N1 viruses circulated widely in the U.S. pig population. However, in 1998, H3N2 viruses from humans were introduced into the pig population and caused widespread disease among pigs [2].

Avian influenza viruses may be transmitted to humans in two main ways: Directly from birds or from avian virus-contaminated environments to people or through an intermediate host, such as a pig.

Influenza viruses have eight separate gene segments. The segmented genome allows viruses from different species to mix and create a new influenza A virus if viruses from two different species infect the same person or animal. For example, if a pig were infected with a human influenza virus and an avian influenza virus at the same time, the viruses could reassort and produce a new virus that had most of the genes from the human virus, but a hemagglutinin and/or neuraminidase from the avian virus (Antigenic shift). The resulting new virus might then be able to infect humans and spread from person to person, but it would have surface proteins (hemagglutinin and/or neuraminidase) not previously seen in influenza viruses that infect humans. . If this new virus causes illness in people and can be transmitted easily from person to person, an influenza pandemic can occur. It also is possible that the process of reassortment could occur in a human. A person could be infected with avian influenza and a human strain of

influenza at the same time. These viruses could reassort to create a new virus that had a hemagglutinin from the avian virus and other genes from the human virus.

Theoretically, influenza A viruses with a hemagglutinin against which humans have little or no immunity that have reassorted with a human influenza virus are more likely to result in sustained human-to-human transmission and pandemic influenza. [3, 4].

Bird flu is an infection caused by avian (bird) influenza (flu) viruses. These flu viruses occur naturally among birds. Wild birds worldwide carry the viruses in their intestines, but usually do not get sick from them. Bird flu is very contagious among birds and can make some domesticated birds, including chickens, ducks, and turkeys very sick and kill them. Several instances of human infections and outbreaks of avian influenza have been reported since 1997. Most cases of avian influenza infection in humans are thought to have resulted from contact with infected poultry or contaminated surfaces.

Confirmed instances of avian influenza viruses infecting humans since 1997 include:

***Influenza A (H5N1) virus** – also called “H5N1 virus” is influenza A virus subtype that occurs mainly in birds. It was first isolated from birds (terns) in South Africa in 1961. Like all bird flu viruses, H5N1 virus circulates among birds worldwide, is very contagious among birds, and can be deadly.

During the last decade highly pathogenic strains of avian influenza virus, including the H5N1 subtype, crossed the species barriers from birds to

humans and caused fatal disease. The Z strain of H5N1 subtype is characterized by pathogenicity to a larger number of animal species and by resistance to the older class of antiviral drugs. At present, two out of three general conditions for the onset of a pandemic have been met; namely, the emergence of a new virus and its ability to replicate in humans causing serious illness.

Outbreaks of influenza H5N1 occurred among poultry in eight countries in Asia (Cambodia, China, Indonesia, Japan, Laos, South Korea, Thailand, and Vietnam) during late 2003 and early 2004. At that time, more than 100 million birds in the affected countries either died from the disease or were killed in order to try to control the outbreak. By March 2004, the outbreak was reported to be under control. Beginning in late June 2004, however, new deadly outbreaks of influenza H5N1 among poultry were reported by several countries in Asia (Cambodia, China, Indonesia, Malaysia [first-time reports], Thailand, and Vietnam). It is believed that these outbreaks are ongoing [5, 6].

Avian influenza A (H5N1) infections occurred in both poultry and humans for the first time in Hong Kong, 1997. During this outbreak, 18 people were hospitalized and six of them died. To control the outbreak, authorities killed about 1.5 million chickens to remove the source of the virus. Scientists determined that the virus spread primarily from birds to humans, though rare person-to-person infection was noted

In 2003 Two cases of avian influenza A (H5N1) infection occurred among members of a Hong Kong family that had traveled to China. One person recovered, the other died. How or where these two family members were infected

was not determined. Another family member died of a respiratory illness in China, but no testing was done. From December 30, 2003, to March 17, 2004, 12 confirmed human cases of avian influenza A (H5N1) were reported in Thailand and 23 in Vietnam, resulting in a total of 23 deaths. Again, beginning in late June 2004, new lethal outbreaks of H5N1 among poultry were reported by several countries in Asia. The new outbreaks of H5N1 in poultry in Asia were followed by renewed sporadic reporting of human cases of H5N1 infection in Vietnam and Thailand beginning in August and continuing into 2005. In one isolated instance, probable limited human-to-human transmission occurred in Thailand in September [7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13].

***Avian influenza A H9N2** illness was confirmed in two children in China and Hong Kong, 1999. Both patients recovered, and no additional cases were confirmed. Poultry was the source of infection. However, the possibility of person-to-person transmission could not be ruled out. Several additional human H9N2 infections were reported from mainland China in 1998-99.

***H7N2**, Virginia, 2002: Following an outbreak of H7N2 among poultry in the Shenandoah Valley poultry production area, one person was found to have serologic evidence of infection with H7N2.

***H7N7**, Netherlands, 2003: The Netherlands reported outbreaks of influenza A (H7N7) in poultry on several farms. Later, infections were reported among pigs and humans. In total, 89 people were confirmed to have H7N7 influenza virus infection

associated with this poultry outbreak. These cases occurred mostly among poultry workers. H7N7-associated illness included 78 cases of conjunctivitis (eye infections) only; 5 cases of conjunctivitis and influenza-like illnesses with cough, fever, and muscle aches; 2 cases of influenza-like illness only; and 4 cases that were classified as "other." There was one death among the 89 total cases. The death occurred in a veterinarian who visited one of the affected farms and developed acute respiratory distress syndrome and complications related to H7N7 infection. The majority of these cases occurred as a result of direct contact with infected poultry; however, Dutch authorities reported three possible instances of transmission from poultry workers to family members. Since that time, no other instances of H7N7 infection among humans have been reported [14, 15].

***H9N2**, Hong Kong, 2003: H9N2 infection was confirmed in a child in Hong Kong. The child was hospitalized but recovered.

***H7N2**, New York: In November 2003, a patient with serious underlying medical conditions was admitted to a hospital in New York with respiratory symptoms. One of the initial laboratory tests identified influenza A virus that was thought to be H1N1. The patient recovered and went home after a few weeks. Subsequent confirmatory tests conducted in March 2004 showed that the patient had been infected with an H7N2 avian influenza virus. An investigation to determine the source of infection is ongoing.

***H7N3** in Canada, 2004: In February 2004, human infections of H7N3 among poultry workers were associated with an H7N3 outbreak among poultry. The H7N3-associated illnesses consisted of eye infections. Surveillance identified two persons with confirmed avian influenza infection. Symptoms included conjunctivitis and mild influenza like illness [16]

Symptoms of Avian Influenza in Humans

The reported symptoms of avian influenza in humans have ranged from typical influenza-like symptoms (e.g., fever, cough, sore throat, and muscle aches) to eye infections (conjunctivitis), pneumonia, acute respiratory distress, viral pneumonia, and other severe and life-threatening complications. These symptoms are associated with lymphopenia. Avian influenza has been reported in a patient with fever and diarrhea but no respiratory symptoms. Avian influenza should be included in the differential diagnosis for patients with predominantly gastrointestinal symptoms, particularly if they have a history of exposure to poultry [17, 18].

Infection of children: Influenza viruses from chickens (H5N1) have caused outbreaks in children from both Vietnam and Thailand in 2004. All infected patients presented with fever and cough. Striking laboratory findings included leukopenia and thrombocytopenia. All children who developed progressive pneumonia with acute respiratory distress syndrome died. However, very few children received antiviral therapy [19, 20].

The diagnosis of influenza A (H5N1)

In many of the reported patients the diagnosis of influenza A (H5N1) was confirmed by means of viral culture or reverse transcriptase-polymerase chain reaction with primers specific for H5 and N1[18,21]

Antiviral Agents for Influenza

Four different influenza antiviral drugs (amantadine, rimantadine, oseltamivir, and zanamivir) are approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for the treatment and/or prophylaxis of influenza. All four have activity against influenza A viruses. However, sometimes influenza strains can become resistant to these drugs, and therefore the drugs may not always be effective. For example, analyses of some of the 2004 H5N1 viruses isolated from poultry and humans in Asia have shown that the viruses are resistant to two of the medications (amantadine and rimantadine). Monitoring of avian viruses for resistance to influenza antiviral medications is ongoing.

The efficacy of the neuraminidase inhibitor GS4104 (oseltamivir phosphate) against these H5N1 and H9N2 viruses has been demonstrated in mice. GS4071 (the active metabolite of oseltamivir) inhibited viral replication in MDCK cells (EC₅₀ values, 7.5-12 microM) and neuraminidase activity (IC₅₀ values, 7.0-15 nM).

When orally administered at doses of 1 and 10 mg/kg per day, GS4104 prevented death of mice infected with A/Hong Kong/156/97 (H5N1), mouse-

adapted A/Quail/Hong Kong/G1/97 (H9N2), or human A/Hong Kong/1074/99 (H9N2) viruses and

reduced virus titers in the lungs and prevented the spread of virus to the brain of mice infected with A/Hong Kong/156/97 (H5N1) and mouse-adapted A/Quail/Hong Kong/G1/97 (H9N2) viruses. When therapy was delayed until 36 h after exposure to the H5N1 virus, GS4104 was still effective and significantly increased the number of survivors as compared with control. Oral administration of GS4104 (0.1 mg/kg per day) in combination with rimantadine (1 mg/kg per day) reduced the number of deaths of mice infected with 100 MLD (50) of H9N2 virus and prevented the deaths of mice infected with 5 MLD (50) of virus [22].

The orally administered neuraminidase (NA) inhibitor RWJ-270201, zanamivir, and oseltamivir have been shown in mice to inhibit avian influenza viruses NA activity and replication in tissue culture and have protective effect against lethal H5N1 and H9N2 virus infection. In vitro, NA inhibition by RWJ-270201 (50% inhibitory concentration, 0.9 to 4.3 nM) was superior to that by zanamivir and oseltamivir carboxyl ate. RWJ-270201 inhibited the replication of avian influenza viruses of both Eurasian and American lineages in MDCK cells (50% effective concentration, 0.5 to 11.8 microM). Mice given 10 mg of RWJ-270201 per kg of body weight per day were completely protected against lethal challenge with influenza A/Hong Kong/156/97 (H5N1) and A/quail/Hong Kong/G1/97 (H9N2) viruses. Both RWJ-270201 and oseltamivir significantly reduced virus titers in mouse lungs at daily dosages of 1.0 and 10 mg/kg and prevented the spread of virus to the brain. When treatment began 48 h after exposure to H5N1 virus, 10 mg of RWJ-270201/kg/day protected 50% of mice

from death. RWJ-270201, zanamivir or oseltamivir can be of potential clinical use for treatment of emerging influenza viruses that may be transmitted from birds to humans [23].

The risk to humans from bird flu

The risk from bird flu is generally low to most people because the viruses occur mainly among birds and do not usually infect humans. However, during an outbreak of bird flu among poultry (domesticated chicken, ducks, turkeys), there is a possible risk to people who have contact with infected birds or surfaces that have been contaminated with excretions from infected birds. The current outbreak of avian influenza A (H5N1) among poultry in Asia (see below) is an example of a bird flu outbreak that has caused human infections and deaths. In such situations, people should avoid contact with infected birds or contaminated surfaces, and should be careful when handling and cooking poultry.

References

- 1-Hayden F, Croisier A. transmission of Avian Influenza Viruses to and between Humans. *J Infect Dis.* 2005 Oct 15; 192(8):1311-4. Epub 2005 Sep 12.
- 2-DolinR. Influenza. In: Harrison's Principles of Internal Medicine. 2003; 15 th ed Part 7, Section 13. DNA and RNA Respiratory viruses. CD-ROM, <http://www.harrisonsonline.com/>
- 3-Molinari JA. Avian influenza: viral emergence and potential for human disease. *Compend Contin Educ Dent.* 2005; 26(9):670, 672, 674-5.
- 4-Shaw M, Cooper L, Xu X, Thompson W, Krauss S, Guan Y. Molecular changes associated with the transmission of avian influenza A H5N1 and H9N2 viruses to humans. *J Med Virol.* 2002 Jan; 66(1):107-14.

- 5-de Jong MD, Hien TT. Avian influenza A (H5N1). *J Clin Virol*. 2005 Oct 4; [Epub ahead of print].
- 6- de la Barrera CA, Reyes-Teran G. Influenza: forecast for a pandemic. *Arch Med Res*. 2005; 36(6):628-36
- 7-Ligon BL. Avian Influenza Virus H5N1: A Review of Its History and Information Regarding Its Potential to Cause the Next Pandemic. *Semin Pediatr Infect Dis*. 2005 Oct; 16(4):326-35
8. www.cdc.gov/flu/avian/outbreaks/asia.htm
<http://www.oie.int/>, <http://www.who.int/en/>
- 9-Beigel JH, Farrar J, Han AM, Hayden FG, Hyer R, de Jong MD. Avian influenza A (H5N1) infection in humans. *N Engl J Med*. 2005 29; 353(13):1374-85.
- 10-Maines TR, Lu XH, Erb SM, Edwards L, Guarner J, Greer PW. Avian influenza (H5N1) viruses isolated from humans in Asia in 2004 exhibit increased virulence in mammals. *J Virol*. 2005; 79(18):11788-800.
11. www.cdc.gov/flu/avian/outbreaks/asia.htm,
<http://www.oie.int/>, and <http://www.who.int/en/>
- 12-Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Cases of influenza A (H5N1)--Thailand, 2004. *MMWR Morb Mortal Wkly Rep*. 2004 Feb 13; 53(5):100-3.
- 13-Guan Y, Poon LL, Cheung CY, Ellis TM, Lim W, Lipatov AS, Chan KH. H5N1 influenza: a protean pandemic threat. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2004 5; 101(21):8156-61.
- 14-de Wit E, Munster VJ, Spronken MI, Bestebroer TM. Protection of mice against lethal infection with highly pathogenic H7N7 influenza A virus by using a recombinant low-pathogenicity vaccine strain. *Beyer WE. J Virol*. 2005; 79(19):12401-7.
- 15-Fouchier RA, Schneeberger PM, Rozendaal FW, Broekman JM, Kemink SA, Munste. Avian influenza A virus (H7N7) associated with human conjunctivitis and a fatal case of acute respiratory distress syndrome. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2004 Feb 3; 101(5):1356-61. Epub 2004 Jan 16
- 16-Tweed SA, Skowronski DM, David ST, Larder A, Petric M, Lees W. Human illness from avian influenza H7N3, British Columbia. *Emerg Infect Dis*. 2004 Dec; 10(12):2196-9.
- 17-Tran TH, Nguyen TL, Nguyen TD, Luong TS, Pham PM, Nguyen VC et al. Avian influenza A (H5N1) in 10 patients in Vietnam. *N Engl J Med*. 2004 Mar 18; 350(12):1179-88. Epub 2004 ;25
- 18-Apisarnthanarak A, Kitphati R, Thongphubeth K, Patoomanunt P, Anthanont P, Auwanit W et al. Atypical avian influenza (H5N1). *Emerg Infect Dis*. 2004 Jul; 10(7):1321-4.
- 19-Grose C, Chokephaibulkit K. Avian influenza virus infection of children in Vietnam and Thailand. *Pediatr Infect Dis J*. 2004 Aug; 23(8):793-4.
- 20-Chokephaibulkit K, Uprasertkul M, Puthavathana P, Chearskul P, Auewarakul P, et al. A child with avian influenza A (H5N1) infection. *Pediatr Infect Dis J*. 2005 Feb; 24(2):162-6.
- 21-Payungporn S, Phakdeewirot P, Chutinimitkul S, Theamboonlers A, Keawcharoen J, Oraveerakul K et al. Single-step multiplex reverse transcription-polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) for influenza A virus subtype H5N1 detection. *Viral Immunol*. 2004;17(4):588-93
- 22-Leneva IA, Roberts N, Govorkova EA, Goloubeva OG, Webster The neuraminidase inhibitor GS4104 (oseltamivir phosphate) is efficacious against A/Hong Kong/156/97 (H5N1) and A/Hong Kong/1074/99 (H9N2) influenza viruses. *RG..*
- 23-Govorkova EA, Leneva IA, Goloubeva OG, Bush K, Webster RG. Comparison of efficacies of RWJ-270201, zanamivir, and oseltamivir against H5N1, H9N2, and other avian influenza viruses. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother*. 2001 Oct; 45(10):2723-32.
- 24' www.who.int/foodsafety/micro/avian/en

Letter to the Editor

New International Association Formed to Address Global Medical Changes

Bernard Ferguson
President
International Association of Medical Colleges
E.mail:bernard@fergusonjd.net

Bernard Ferguson, JD

The International Association of Medical Colleges Medicine (IAOMC) has been formed to serve as the catalyst for assisting medical hospitals, Licensing Boards, and agencies around the world to effectively function in the ever accelerating inter communication and integration that is a part of the new global world. The mission of this non-stock, not for profit organization is to enhance world wide medical education by means of accreditation under uniform global standards. It is structured to interact in concert with the world's governing regulators. At the present, Association members are medical schools whose standards are ranked by the USDOE as substantially similar to medical schools in the United States. Membership in the IAOMC is open to the 1,684 medical schools currently

listed in the World Health Directory; and members of the 177 known regulatory agencies in the world. IAOMC invitations have been extended to all the world's qualified medical schools and regulatory agencies.

The IAOMC is a global response to the issue of varying medical education standards. It will be the world's first international medical school accreditor. In a challenge to traditional accreditation standards processes, every part of the Association process will be open and transparent. This is the first accreditation organization to end the mystery and secrecy that typically surrounds how most nations maintain medical education standards. Its public accountability will allow everyone to see exactly which schools are maintaining standards and

which ones are not. Everyone can obtain a copy of the Associations reports.

At a time of an ever-worsening physician shortage the Association's member schools responded. Approximately 3,000 of their clinical students are now studying across the United States. For example, IAOMC members have more clinical students

She will address the Association's standards meeting at the NY Hyatt on August 12th in her capacity as the Academic Director of Harvard Medical International. Pledged to be a fully open and democratic association, every medical school in the world within the World Health Directory (1,684) will be contacted for comment.

The Federation of State Medical Boards assisted by providing the list of every known regulatory agency in the world (177). They have each been invited to participate in the Association. Every Mission to the United Nations (190) has been notified to alert the medical schools and regulatory agencies in their nations. And the Regulatory Agencies were heard from. The interest is world wide, a few illustrations. After John P. Lamont, Registrar, of Ireland's Medical Council received notice of the standards meeting,

studying in New York State than the combined totals of Cornell University School of Medicine, Columbia University School of Medicine, NY State University of New York at Rochester, and State University of New York at Stony Brook. One of America's outstanding physicians, Dr. Lynn Eckert, is the Chair of the American Association of Medical Colleges.

and talked to Professor Muiris Fitzgerald, Chair of Education Committee. He has confirmed his attendance. Dorian Shillingford Chair of the Dominican Medical Board confirmed. Sheri Nichols, Alabama's Medical Board Secretary placed the invitation on the next Board meeting agenda. Bulgaria's UN Second Secretary Mrs. Anna Ruski will accompany Dr. Elena Piperkova from Sofia.

Invitations from the Association has drawn responses from such as Syed Ziaur Rahman, MD of Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College in India to **Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi MD, PhD. Of Al Kadhimiya Teaching Hospital in Iraq** to Michael Gordon from University of Toronto. All have submitted applications to serve as school on site inspectors.

ABO blood groups and breast cancer

Sudad Salman Al Bassam

Specialist General Surgeon
Al Kindi General Hospital
Baghdad Iraq
E-mail:sudadss@yahoo.com

Abstract

Background: Blood group A of the ABO system has been reported to be associated with some Malignancies including breast cancer (Ca). However, reports of the association of breast cancer Ca with various blood group have been conflicting.

Aim of the study: The aim of this paper is to study the association of breast cancer Ca with various blood groups

Patients and methods: Reviewing the case reports of 395 female patient with histopathological diagnosis of breast Ca whom were observed at the general surgery and oncology units at the University hospital in Al Kadhimiyia and the Nursing house hospital at Baghdad from the period from January 1990 to October 1997. Their ages ranged from 24-83 years (50.97 \pm 12.6). 400 females patients with disease other than malignancy were considered a comparative control.

Results: The distribution of blood groups in patients with breast Ca Table(1) was significantly different from the control group (Chi-square 9.6, Odd difference 3 P < 0.05). In patients with

breast Ca there was a higher prevalence of blood group O than the control group with a significant Chi-square (13.6), (P 0.05) for patients 50 years old and younger (Premenapause). Patients older than 50 years (Postmenapouse) showed higher prevalence of group B. Familial breast Ca occurred in the premenopausal group

Introduction

Blood group A of the ABO system has been reported to be associated with some Malignancies including GIT malignancies, prostate, cervix, ovary, and breast malignancy [1,2]. Reports of the association of breast Ca with various blood group have been conflicting. George & Chalestry (1969) reported a significant predominance of blood group A in breast cancer patients [3]. Moural et al 1980 & Levin et al 1981 [4, 5] reported that 50 patients with progressive form of breast Ca have blood group A.

Tryggvadottir et al [6] in 1988 reported familial cases have 2 fold prevalence of group B. While the predominance of blood group O has been reported by Newell et al [2].

The association of breast Ca and blood group could have a role in identifying women at risk of developing breast Ca [1].

Patients and methods

Reviewing the case reports of 395 female patient with histopathological diagnosis of breast Ca whom were observed at the general surgery and oncology units at the University hospital in Al Kadhimiyia and the Nursing house hospital at Baghdad from the period from January 1990 to October 1997. Their ages ranged from 24-83 years (50.97 \pm 12.6). 400 females patients with disease other than malignancy were considered a comparative control. Their ages ranged from 20 to 82 years (49.3 \pm 13.7).

Family history: 123 patients (31.6%) have family history of breast Ca affecting first or second degree relatives. 255 patients (64.5%) didn't have family history of breast cancer. While in 17 patients (4.4%) the family history couldn't be determined. More than two third of the patients 83 (67.47%) with positive family history were under the age of 50.

116 (29.4%) patients have no clinical or histological lymph node involvement (stage -1) with 76 patients (65.5%) was under the age of 50 years.

Histopathology: 334 patients with breast cancer (84.6%) have invasive ductal

carcinoma (ductal type) including 9 patients with carcinoma in situ and 4 with Pagets disease, 60 patients (15.2 %) have lobular carcinoma, and one patients with cystosarcoma phylloides. 68.6% have moderately differentiating carcinoma.

Results

The distribution of blood groups in patients with breast Ca Table(1) was significantly different from the control group (Chi-square 9.6, Odd difference 3 P < 0.05). In patients with breast Ca there was a higher prevalence of blood group O than the control group with a significant Chi-square (13.6), (P 0.05) for patients 50 years old and younger (Pre-menopause). Patients older than 50 years (Post-menopause) showed higher prevalence of group B. Familial breast Ca occurred in the pre-menopausal group. The ABO blood groups of patients with familial breast Ca were statistically different (Chi-square 27.2, P < 0.05, Odd ratio 3) from the non-familial cases table (1). There was no association between the histopathological type or the stage of the disease (lymph node involvement) any and specific blood group Table (2). Only 2 patients have bilateral involvement including 2 patients with poorly differentiated invasive Ca associated with AB and, A blood groups respectively. 87 patients have Ca on the left side including 3 patients with fibroadenoma on the right side, 2 of them have blood group B and one has blood group O.

Blood Group	Breast CA patients	≤<50 years	>50 years	Familial	Non-familial	Control group
A	98 (24.8%)	56(23.8%)	42(26.2%)	23(18.7%)	70(27.5%)	106(26.5%)
B	124(31.4%)	63(26.8%)	61(38%)	58(47.2 %.)	61(23.9%)	106(26.5%)
O	145(36.7%)	103(43.8%)	42(26.2%)	36(29.3%)	104(40.8%)	134(33.5%)
AB	28(7.1%)	13(5.5%)	15(9.3%)	6(4.8%)	20(7.8%)	54(13.5%)
Total	395(100%)	235(100%)	160(100%)	123(100%)	255(100%)	400(100%)

Table (1): Distribution of blood groups in patients with breast CA and the controls

Blood group	Histopathology		Stage (1)	LN involvement (+)
	Ductal	Lobular		
A	78(26. %) 11(18.3%)		31(26.7%)	67(24%)
B	104(31%)	19(31.7%)	33(28.4%)	91(36.2%)
O	118(35%)	27(45%)	48(41.3)	97(34.7%)
AB	25(7.5%)	3 (5%)	4 (3.4%)	24(8.6%)
Total	334	60	116	279

Table (2): Distribution of blood groups in patients with breast CA according to the histopathological types and lymph node (LN) involvement

Discussion

The age difference of the distribution of blood groups in this study agrees with finding of Anderson DE 1971[7], although he reported his observations on familial breast Ca and considered 45 years is the menopausal age. However our finding of higher incidence of blood group B in postmenopausal women contradicts the finding of Anderson of group A higher incidence in this group. However such difference could be attributed to the differing prevalence of

blood groups in different communities. In contrast to the observation of George P, Chalestry LJ of higher prevalence of group A among breast Ca patients, our patients have higher prevalence of blood groups B and O. The higher prevalence of blood group B in this study agrees with observation of Tryggvadottir L et al [6], who reported 2 fold higher prevalence of blood group B in familial breast Ca compared with the sporadic cases.

References

- 1-Anderson DE, Haas C. Blood group A and familial breast cancer 1984; (54):1855-1860.
- 2-Newell GR, Gordon JE, Molezun AP, Horwit JS. ABO blood groups and cancer. *J Nat Cancer Invest* 1974; (52):1425-1430.
- 3- George P, Chalestry LJ. Factors in the diagnosis of breast disease. *British J Surg* 1969; (56):337-341.
- 4- Mourali N, Muenz LR, Tabbane F. Epidemiologic features of rapid progressive breast cancer in Tunisia. *Cancer* 1980 ; (46):2741-2746.
- 5-Levin PH, Mourali N, Tabbane F. Studies on the role of cellular immunity and genetics in biology of rapidly progressing breast cancer in Tunisia. *Int J Cancer* 1981; (27):611-615.
- 6-Tryggvadottir L, Tulinius H, Robertson JM. Familial and sporadic breast cancer in Iceland: A comparison related to ABO blood groups and risk of bilateral breast cancer. *Int J Cancer* 1988; (42): 499-501.
- 7-Anderson D. Some characteristics of familial breast cancer *Cancer* 1971 ; (28): 1500-1504.

Acknowledgement: The author acknowledges the great help of the editor Dr Aamir Jalal Al Mosawi in the preparation of this paper to make it suitable for publication

The value of diagnostic laparoscopy in chronic peritonitis of unknown origin

Ahmed Al Mazaar
Specialist surgeon
Al Kadhimiyia teaching hospital
Baghdad, Iraq

Abstract

Background: The etiology of chronic peritonitis remains some times undetermined and laboratory tests including ascetic fluid analysis are not specific nor diagnostic. Anti-tuberculosis therapeutic trial some times justified. The aim of this study is to determine the diagnostic value of laparoscopy in such cases,

Patients and Methods: Forty patients, 15 males (37.5%) and 25 females (62.5%) with chronic peritonitis were admitted from December 1995 to June 1999 at the Gastroenterology center of Baghdad teaching Hospital. The origin of peritonitis remained unknown as laboratory tests including ascetic fluid analysis showed non specific findings. Their mean age was 37.5 year. 36 patients undergone laparoscopic examination.

The patients were studied retrospectively and prospectively to determine the possible diagnostic value of laparoscopy in such cases

Results: The maximum age incidence of the patients was between 20-39 years (52.5%) Abdominal distension and abdominal pain were the commonest presenting symptoms. Abdominal distension and tenderness were the

commonest abdominal signs. 9 patients (22.5%) have of pulmonary abnormalities and pleural effusion. 3 patients (7.5 %) have diabetes and one patient have cirrhosis. of the 36 patients undergone laparoscopic examination: ascites with bowel and peritoneal adhesions were present in 18 patients (50%), ascites with multiple whitish nodules and omental thickening in 12 patients (33.3%), bowel thickening with visceral adhesions without ascites in 2 patients (5.5%), female reproductive organs involvement with peritoneal nodules in 2 patients (5.5%), and peritoneal nodules with hepatic involvement in 2 patients (5.5%).

Conclusion: The laparoscopic findings were non specific and the procedure is of no diagnostic value.

Introduction

The etiology of chronic peritonitis remains some times undetermined and laboratory tests including ascetic fluid analysis are not specific nor did diagnostic. Anti-tuberculosis therapeutic trial some times justify. The aim of this study is to determine the diagnostic value of laparoscopy in such cases.

Patients and Methods: Forty patients, 15 males (37.5%) and 25 females (62.5%) with chronic peritonitis were admitted from December 1995 to June 1999 at the Gastroenterology center of Baghdad teaching Hospital. The origin of peritonitis remained unknown as laboratory tests including ascitic fluid analysis showed non specific findings. Their mean age was 37.5 year. 36 patients undergone laparoscopic examination. The patients were studied retrospectively and prospectively to determine the possible diagnostic value of laparoscopy in such cases

.24 patients (60%) were living in Baghdad, 9 patients (22.5%) were living in the North of Iraq and 7 patients (17.5%) were living in the south of Iraq.

Results: The maximum age incidence of the patients was between 20-39 years (52.5%)The presenting symptom was abdominal distension in 29 patients(72.5%),abdominal pain in 15(37.5%) patients, fever in 8(20%) patients, jaundice in 5(12%) patients, weight loss in 4(10%) patients ,abdominal mass in 1 patient, acute abdomen in 1 patient, and generalize weakness in 1 patient.15 patients (37.5%) presented within 1 month or less from the start of symptom.23 patients (55.5%) were symptomatic for 2-6 months before presentation ,and 2 patients(5%) have symptoms for more than 7 months on presentation. On examination 37 patients (92.5%) have abdominal distension,38 patients (95%) have peritonitis,37 (92.5%) have generalized wasting,27(67.5%) have fever,21 patients(52.5%) have abdominal tenderness,9 patients(22.5%) have heptomegaly ,8 patients (20%) have heatosplenomegaly.3 patients (7.5%) have abdominal mass, 3 patients

(7.5%) have jaundice, and 1 patient have axillary lymphadenopathy. 9 patients (22.5%) have of pulmonary changes, and pleural effusion.3 patients (7.5%) have diabetes and one patient have cirrhosis.

Abdominal ultrasound showed ascitic fluid in 33 patients (82.5%),organomegaly (heptomegaly with or without splenomegaly) in 18 patients (45%),peritoneal adhesion and bowel thickening in 9 patients (22.5%),abdominal mass in 3 patients (7.5%),and abdominal lymph node enlargement in one patient.36 patients undergone laparoscopic examination:ascites with bowel and peritoneal adhesions were present in 18 patients (50%),ascites with multiple whitish nodules and omental thickening in 12 patients(33.3%),bowel thickening with visceral adhesions without ascites in 2 patients (5.5%),female reproductive organs involvement with peritoneal nodules in 2 patients (5.5%),and peritoneal nodules with hepatic involvement in 2 patients (5.5%).

Discussion: The laparoscopic findings in this study were similar to laparoscopic finding in patients with TB peritonitis [1]; however these findings are neither specific nor diagnostic. The diagnostic laparoscopy in patients with chronic peritonitis of unknown origin is unlikely to be of significant value as the findings are largely non specific. Continued follow up of such patients could more helpful in such cases.

References

1-Rodreigues de Lope C, San Miguel.Laprosopical diagnosis of tuberculosis ascites.Endoscopy 1982; 14(5):178-179.